

Stitch Reminder' To Prevent and Decrease the Incidence of 'Forgotten Stent' Cases: A Retrospective Study**Arvind Kumar****Department of Urology and Renal Transplant, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, M.P., India****Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024****Corresponding Author: Dr. Arvind Kumar****Conflict of interest: Nil****Abstract:****Objective:** With increasing practice in urology, use of double j stents has widely increased for various indications and simultaneously increased incidence of forgotten stents too.**Methods:** We are presenting a simple, cheap and comfortable 'Stitch reminder' technique to prevent forgotten stent. For it, we left the suture in situ in per cutaneous nephrolithotomy cases and took a single, non-absorbable, subcuticular suture to right or left flank region as 'stitch reminder' for non-percutaneous nephrolithotomy cases.**Results:** We retrospectively evaluated such cases between May 2020 to March 2023. 578 such patients in which stents and 'stitch reminder' were placed were evaluated. Their demographic profile, indications for stenting, stent removed or not were recorded. 557 patients came for follow up and both stent and stitch removed. 17 patients died of their primary illness and one patient couldn't be traced.**Conclusions:** So 'Stitch reminder' technique we used is safe, effective, economical with no complication and also effective in preventing 'forgotten and retained stents' and associated complications.**Keywords:** Double J Stent, Stitch Reminder, Per Cutaneous Nephrolithotomy.

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Introduction

Double J stent (DJS) has been widely used in urology practice since 1967 [1]. It is commonly used for both endoscopic and open urological surgeries and also used for non-urological indications [2,3]. Ureteral stent should also be removed when the treating physician asks for removal after certain time period, even then stents may be overlooked and forgotten by patient.

The long-term retention of stents in urinary tract may lead to complications such as fragmentation, encrustation, stone formation, urinary tract infection (UTI)[4] and some of them could lead to pyonephrosis and nephrectomy with difficult management.

To prevent such complications we are presenting a simple, cheap and comfortable 'Stitch reminder' technique.

Materials and Methods

Between May 2020 to March 2023, 578 patients presented to us for DJS for various indications i. e. Obstructive uropathy due to bilateral or unilateral stone disease, pelviureteric junction obstruction,

with or without renal failure, Post-operative cases after per cutaneous stone treatment(PNL), ureteroscopic removal of stone(URS), retrograde intra renal surgery(RIRS), open and laparoscopic renal surgeries and ureteral reconstructive surgeries and cervical malignancies in female with end stage renal diseases. In all such patients we recorded their demographic profile as well. Bilateral stents were placed in 166 cases.

Methods

We used our 'Stitch reminder' technique in all patients who underwent DJ stenting. The technique was simple as we left stitch in PNL cases where single renal puncture was required or left one or two sutures where multiple punctures were required to clear the stones, took a subcutaneous non-absorbable suture either in right or left flank in which side stent placed as 'Stitch reminder' in non PNL, URS, RIRS and laparoscopic cases and left one or two stitches at incision site in open urological surgery cases where stent was placed. For bilateral endoscopic cases we left or took sutures on both sides of flank.

Figure 1: Showing post PNL stitch and double J stent removal

Results

In our study, we analysed all patients in which DJS were placed at our centre. Patients demographic profile, indications for stenting, unilateral or bilateral and complications if any developed after stenting were evaluated retrospectively. Age of patients were between 19-72 years with mean age of 46.21 years. Male to female ratio and rural to urban ratio was 2:1. Most common indication for stenting was after urological surgery followed by obstructive

uropathy. Unilateral or bilateral stenting ratio was 2.5:1. We followed our 'Stitch reminder' technique in all patients treated and stented. Stent related discomfort, urinary tract infection and mild hematuria developed post operatively and managed conservatively. 2 patients developed moderate to severe hematuria and managed with blood transfusion.

All patients were followed up for stent removal or exchange and we achieved stent removal/exchange rate of 96.36% in our study.

Table 1:

Age(yrs)	19-72 yrs
Sex(M:F)	2:1
Rural: Urban	2:1
UL/BL Stenting	2.5:1
Indications for DJS	Post-operative- 371 Obstructive uropathy-157 Prophylactic DJS- 2 Others-48
Complications if any	Stent related discomfort-90 UTI- 60, Hematuria- Mild- 30, Moderate to severe- 2

Discussion

Double J stent placement in urinary tract is common now a days as day to day urological practice is rising especially in endourology, laser stone treatment and laparoscopic renal surgeries. With it, incidence of retained or forgotten stents is also rising. Divakaruni N et al. reported approximately 12% of all ureteral DJ stents are retained or forgotten in their study [5]. Various factors for retained or forgotten stent are patient load of health care centre, education level of patient and his socio economic status, patient negligence, not mentioning about DJS in situ in discharge card etc.

Retained or forgotten stent leads to complications like recurrent UTI and sepsis, stent encrustation or stone formation, chronic renal diseases and renal failure [6,7]. Most of the patients were from rural background with low education level and low socio economic group in our study so we used 'Stitch reminder' technique in our patients which is economical, effective and safe without any complications. The chief advantage of our technique is very simple reminder that stitch is nonabsorbable hence it needs removal so patient was told to follow up for stitch in situ hence the patient remembers what we told him in local language as 'taar', 'satak', 'pipe'

or 'tube' inside the body which needs removal or exchange on time. Various methods for stent reminder to the patient and treating physician were used in past. Monga et.al. [8] and McCahey and Ramsden [9], demonstrated a reduction in the number of overdue DJ stents from 3.6% to 1.1%. In India, Sabharwal et al. proposed a novel online registry system in 2014 [10]. But their main disadvantage was requirement of specific programmes, access to the hospital network and extra costs in this process.

Mobile based application was used by Mohina et al., including 194 patients and by Zeimba et al., including 115 patients in 2017. They used Ureteral Stent Tracker (UST) developed by Visible Health Inc. (Austin, TX, USA) in partnership with Boston Scientific [11,12]. Both studies showed promising results with almost a 90% plus timely removal of stents [13]. In 2019, Ulker V et al. followed up 87 patients with indwelling DJ stents. Group 1 was followed up using Ureteral stent tracker (UST) application while the Group 2 was followed up with normal paper discharge cards. Group 1 had significantly less overdue times ($p=0.001$) and lost to follow-up cases ($p=0.001$) compared to group 2(13). "Urostentz" has also recently been developed to decrease forgotten stent incidences which used short message service (SMS) technique for stents removal [14].

Conclusion

'Stitch reminder' technique we used is simple, safe, effective, economical with no complications for stent removal and also effective in preventing 'forgotten or retained stent' and its associated complications.

List of abbreviations

- DJS- Double J stent,
- UTI- Urinary tract infection,
- PNL- Per cutaneous nephrolithotomy,
- URS- Ureteroscopic removal of stone,
- RIRS- Retrograde intra renal surgery,
- UST- Ureteral Stent Tracker,
- SMS- Short message service

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